

DETERMINANTS OF SMOKING AMONG THE STUDENTS OF THE TWO MEDICAL SCHOOLS IN MOSUL CITY – IRAQ**Dr. Jeehan Shaker Hassan*, Dr. Bashar Hashim Abbass*, Dr. Rajaa Sadoon Sachet***

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ABSTRACT

To determine the commonest personal and familial risk factors of smoking among medical schools students in Mosul city - Iraq. The study conducted among Mosul Medical College and Nineveh Medical College at Mosul University. A case-control design was adopted in this study which was conducted from 1st of December 2011 to 30th of April 2012, for this purpose 234 participants, 117 smoker students (cases) and 117 non-smoker students (controls), who accepted to participate from both colleges and from all grades were included in the study. Age of the participants ranged between 17 – 28 years old. Data were collected using a special questionnaire form which included information about socio-demographic characteristics of the study population, personal and familial risk factors and smoking habit-related questions. Study results illustrate that peers influence ($p = 0.000$), presence of household smokers ($p = 0.000$), jobless father ($p = 0.013$), higher education of student's mother ($p = 0.033$), absence of one or both of the parents ($p = 0.019$) and high monthly income of family ($p = 0.029$) appeared to have important statistically significant positive association with smoking among the medical schools' students. On the other hand, daily participation in physical activities ($p = 0.000$), higher education level of student's father ($p = 0.003$), housewife mother ($p = 0.017$), and nuclear family ($p = 0.002$) were negatively associated with smoking. In conclusion multiple personal, familial and socio-demographic characteristics of students have a role in predisposing medical students in Mosul to smoking habit. The problem need coordinated efforts from the family, school and university.

INTRODUCTION

University students are at high risk of smoking as they become exposed to greater availability of cigarettes and intimate association with smoking peers. At the same time, they face additional social, emotional and educational challenges when they enter the university.^[1,2,3]

Since tobacco use practices and beliefs about tobacco are formed early in life, it becomes interesting to look at the development of tobacco use among medical students, and how their education may have influenced their beliefs and practices.^[4,5]

Different studies showed that cigarette smoking prevalence is quite high among students of health care professionals and health care workers even though they

know the harmful effects of active and passive smoking.^[6,7]

Smoking represents the most readily preventable risk factor for morbidity and mortality. This habit is an important risk factor for coronary artery diseases.^[8]

Smoking uptake is also associated with other unhealthy risk behaviors. Compared to non-smokers, smokers at young ages are more likely to have academic problems, engage in other types of substance abuse such as binge drinking, and engage in delinquent behavior that may continue into late adolescence.^[9,10]

METHODOLOGY**Sampling technique**

The total sample size was 234 participants from both Mosul and Nineveh Medical Colleges. From Mosul

Medical College 170 students, which constitutes 72.6% of the total sample size (168 male and 2 female students), while from Nineveh Medical College there were 64 participants constituting 27.4% of the sample size (48 male and 16 female students). To examine the possible association of an exposure to a certain risk factor, smoker students (cases) 117 and non-smoker students (controls) 117. Both groups were identified, then the proportion of cases and controls that were exposed and not exposed to certain risk factors was determined.

CASE DEFINITION

Cases are students from all grades of two colleges of medicine at University of Mosul, who are currently smoking either cigarette or narghile or both and from both sexes.

Smoking status is established in accordance to the WHO criteria for cigarette smoking and the criteria set by Maziak et al, 2005. For narghile smoking: smokers were subjects who smoked either regularly (≥ 1 cigarette a day and/or ≥ 1 narghile a week) or occasionally (< 1 cigarette a day and/or < 1 narghile a week).^[11,12]

Cigar, pipes and other types of tobacco use which were uncommon in our society not included in this study. So any case that fulfills the criteria was considered a smoker case.

Control definition

Controls are students who are non-smokers, matched for age and sex and from the same college and grade. Ex-

smokers were excluded from this study because of doubtful about the duration of quitting smoking.

Pilot study

A pilot study was conducted during the 1st two weeks of the study period and consisted of 10 cases and 10 controls chosen randomly according to the criteria of cases and controls. The aims of pilot study were;

- To examine the exploration of the data collection tool and to identify any necessary modification.
- To estimate the response rate of students and to detect possible difficulties that might arise during data collection.
- To estimate the approximate time needed for filling in each questionnaire form.

Statistical analysis of data

- Frequencies of occurrence and percentages were calculated.
- Odds ratio (OR) for all risk factors were done and 95% confidence interval have been measured.
- Chi-square (χ^2) test for contingency tables was used to find the statistical associations between cases and controls for the presence or absence of significance at the level of ≤ 0.05 .

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the analysis of the study as a case-control study with considering personal socio-demographic factors, presence of smoker friends is positively associated with smoking status with very high statistically significance (OR = 5.228; C.I. = 2.768 – 9.860; p = 0.000).

Table 1: Distribution of cases and controls according to their personal characteristics.

Residence	Smoking state				Total N=234		P value*	OR	95% C.I.
	Smoker		Non-smoker		No.	%			
	No.	%	No.	%					
Urban	108	46.2%	102	43.6%	210	89.7%	0.196	1.765	0.754 – 4.125
Rural	9	3.8%	15	6.4%	24	10.3%			
Marital status									
Single	108	46.2%	113	48.3%	221	94.4%	0.154	0.425	0.135 – 1.344
Married	9	3.8%	4	1.7%	13	5.6%			
Living									
With family	96	41.0%	97	41.5%	193	82.5%	0.863	0.943	0.480 – 1.850
Away from family	21	9.0%	20	8.5%	41	17.5%			
Smoker friends									
Present	101	43.2%	64	27.4%	165	70.6%	0.000	5.228	2.768 – 9.860
Absent	16	6.8%	53	22.6%	69	29.4%			

Table 2 indicates that There is a significantly negative association of participation in physical activities (OR = 0.202; C.I. = 0.096 – 0.426; p = 0.000).

Table 2: Distribution of cases and controls according to participation in physical activities.

Participation in physical activities	Smoker		Non-smoker		Total N=234		P value*	OR	95% C.I.
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%			
Present	80	34.2%	107	45.7%	187	79.9%	0.000	0.202	0.096 – 0.426
Absent	37	15.8%	10	4.3%	47	20.1%			

Table 3 indicates the analysis of the study considering familial socio-demographic factors of the study population, higher education of student's fathers was significantly negatively associated with smoking of students (OR = 0.330; C.I. = 0.157 – 0.692; p = 0.003). Regarding father's occupation, jobless fathers were statistically significant positive association with it (OR =

2.5; C.I. = 1.206 – 5.176; p = 0.013). The table also shows a positive association significantly of higher educated mothers with student's smoking (OR = 1.774; C.I. = 1.047 - 3.005; p = 0.033), while there was statistically significant negative association of housewife mothers with student's smoking (OR = 0.530; C.I. = 0.314 – 0.896; p = 0.017).

Table 3: Distribution of cases and controls according to their father's and mother's education and occupation.

Father's education	Smoking state				Total N=234		P value*	OR	95% C.I.
	Smoker		Non-smoker		No.	%			
	No.	%	No.	%					
Higher education	89	38.0%	106	45.3%	195	83.3%	0.003	0.330	0.157 – 0.692
Non-higher education	28	11.9%	11	4.7%	39	16.6%			
Father's occupation									
Jobless	26	11.1%	12	5.1%	38	16.2%	0.013	2.500	1.206 – 5.176
Unskilled	6	2.6%	13	5.6%	19	8.2%	0.094	0.432	0.164 – 1.144
Skilled	35	15.0%	30	12.8%	65	27.8%	0.466	1.238	0.700 – 2.189
Professional	50	21.3%	62	26.5%	112	47.8%	0.116	0.662	0.396 – 1.107
Mother's education									
Higher education	78	33.3%	62	26.5%	140	59.8%	0.033	1.774	1.047 – 3.005
Non-higher education	39	16.7%	55	23.5%	94	40.2%			
Mother's occupation									
Housewife	58	24.8%	76	32.5%	134	57.3%	0.017	0.530	0.314 – 0.896
Employed	59	25.2%	41	17.5%	100	42.7%			

Table 4 shows positive association with smoking and if one or more of the parents was dead (OR = 3.294; C.I. = 1.197 – 9.025; p = 0.019). High monthly income of the family and presence of household smokers are

significantly associated positively with smoking (OR = 1.912; C.I. = 1.069 – 3.416; p = 0.029) and (OR = 3.320; C.I. = 1.923 – 5.732; p = 0.000) respectively.

Table 4: Distribution of cases and controls according to some familial factors.

	Smoking state				Total N=234		P value*	OR	95% C.I.
	Smoker		Non-smoker		No.	%			
	No.	%	No.	%					
One of the parents, at least, is dead									
Yes	15	6.4%	5	2.1%	20	8.5%	0.019	3.294	1.197 – 9.025
No	102	43.6%	112	47.9%	214	91.5%			
Monthly income									
High	40	17.1%	25	10.7%	65	27.8%	0.029	1.912	1.069 – 3.416
Medium	70	30.0%	83	35.5%	153	65.5%	0.074	0.610	0.355 – 1.049
Low	7	2.9%	9	3.8%	16	6.7%	0.604	0.764	0.284 – 2.054
Household smokers									
Present	65	27.8%	32	13.7%	97	41.5%	0.000	3.320	1.923 – 5.732
Absent	52	22.2%	85	36.3%	137	58.5%			

DISCUSSION

Analytic approach of personal and familial factors

Regarding personal and family- related factors which are the main concern of this study; 210 out of 234 students (89.7%) of the study population were living in urban area and 24 students which represent 10.3% of the total population were living in rural area, there was no significant statistical association between residence and smoking state of the students with p value more than 0.05.

The absence of an association between the residential background and the tobacco use highlights the

importance of the spread of the epidemic of tobacco use. Similar observations have been made in the male medical students in 1989^[13], done in India and in another similar study on the young boys in the general population of Uttar Pradesh, 2001.^[14]

Regarding marital status and smoking state of the students, the results in this respect was insignificant with p value more than 0.05, and this report of such result simulate the result reported in Egypt by El-Sharkawy, 2011.^[15]

In this study Peers influence shows that there was about five times risk for presence of smoker friends with very high statistically significant association p value = 0.000, the percentage of smoker students who had smoker friends was 43.2% while among non-smoker students was 27.4%, so participation with friends represented one of the main motives for smoking agreeing with researches done by Mandil *et al.*, 2007 in Sharjah, UAE^[16] and in Egypt by El-Sharkawy, 2011^[15] pointing to the strong influence of peers and friends.

Presence of household smokers are significantly about three times risk for smoking with p value equal to 0.000, this result indicate that presence of a negative role model inside the home in the form of a household smoker play an important role in influence of students for smoking.

These results agreeing with many researches among university and younger students; Mukhtar *et al.*, 2006 in Qalyobia, Egypt^[17] and Mandil *et al.*, 2007^[16] in Sharjah, UAE which reported that youth who lived in a household with adults who smoked were much more likely to smoke.

The influence of friends and family is not surprising, given that young people start smoking largely because of social reasons such as peer pressure. The overwhelming effect of peer pressure on the initiation of tobacco use is a matter of serious concern because it is very difficult to prevent the effect of this factor in an age group which likes the company of their friends as well as is influenced maximally by them. The web of causation of this particular factor is very complicated and it has a direct as well as an indirect and synergistic effect with other factors. Disentangling it would require even more in-depth research.

It was found in this study that there was a significant protective effect of participation in physical activities with p value equal to 0.000. Also the study found that the percentage of students participated in physical activities daily among smoker students was 12.8 % in comparison to 43.3% among non-smoker students, while infrequent participation in physical activities among smoker students was 29.9% in comparison to 13.9% among non-smoker students, so daily physical activities found to be act as a protective factor from smoking with very high statistically significant association with p value equal to 0.000. In Egypt, El-Sharkawy, 2011^[15], found that non participation in physical activities were significantly higher among smokers and this is attributed to different types of influence such as participation in physical activities - if properly done- enables students to make use of time in a useful manner and take them away from long exposure to the effect of peers and friends and spending a lot of time outside the home which may encourage smoking.

Regarding the effect of education of student's father, it appeared that higher education level of student's father is

significantly protective factor with p value equal to= 0.003, the explanation applied for this result could be the paternal supervision, the good paternal knowledge of smoking hazards and the paternal interest in his sons' and daughters' concerns.

This also comes in consistence with the findings of Hann and Asghar, 1997^[18], they stated that the higher the fathers' education, the lower the prevalence of smoking among their children.

While regarding father's occupation, jobless father was statistically significant risk for smoking among students with p value equal to 0.013, while there was no significant association among other types of occupations. Results obtained in this study agree with results done among United Arab Emirate university students reported by Mandil *et al.*, 2007.^[16]

In contrast, regarding mother's education and occupation, it has been found a significant association about two times risk for higher educated mother with p value equal to 0.033.

Also it has been appeared that there is statistically significant protective effect of housewife mother against student's smoking with p value equal to 0.017. These results could be due to that higher level education and mother's employment made them busy and not aware enough with the rapid progression of smoking problem among youth and decreasing age of smoking initiation, also they may have no time to speak and share activities with their sons in addition to providing them with much money and this is agreeing with Challier and his colleagues, 2000^[19], in France who found that the mother being a housewife was a protective factor against smoking but with no marked role for the father's occupation, In addition to that, this is agreeing with a previous report in Egypt by Nassar H, 2003.^[20]

Emphasis on the importance of enjoying the family life also has been revealed in this study as living with family play an insignificant protective role with p value more than 0.05, this result is incompatible with findings of El-Sharkawy, 2011^[15], in which she found the percentage of students living away from their family among smokers is 16.9% compared to 2.8% among non-smokers with high statistical significance and increased risk to 7 times coinciding with other research results.

Regarding the importance of family and parental supervision, the study reported that if one of the parents, at least, is dead it was found to be significantly three times risk factor p value equal to 0.019.

Whereas Nuclear family was found to be have significant protective effect in contrast with extended family with p value equal to 0.002, this could be attributed to the preventive effect of parental supervision on the use of tobacco and the effect of small family size of nuclear

type in comparison with extended family which was quite evident in this study and other similar study in Orissa by Ramakrishna *et al.*, 2005^[21] and in Pakistan by Nawaz *et al.*, 2007.^[22]

Significance of association between smoking of the students and high monthly income of their families found to be about two times risk for smoking of student with *p* value equal to 0.029. This result agrees with results of previous studies Mukhtar *et al.*, 2006^[17] and Mandil *et al.*, 2007^[16], as extra-money encourages expending money on cigarettes but alone can't be the motive.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Multiple personal, familial and socio-demographic characteristics of students have a role in predisposing medical students in Mosul to smoking.
2. The findings of this study re-emphasize the great significance of peers pressure on smoking among medical students of both sexes, and also refer to the importance of presence of a negative role model inside the home in the form of smoker family members in influencing such behavior.
3. Daily participation in physical activities was negatively associated with smoking behavior.
4. Higher level education of student's father is significantly had negative association. While jobless father was statistically had significant positive association with smoking among students.
5. The study found a significant positive association between higher level education of mothers and smoking of students, also it was appeared that housewife mother, small size family and nuclear type of family were statistically had significant negative association with student's smoking.
6. Regarding the importance of parental supervision, the study reported that if one of the parents, at least, is dead it was positively associated with this habit significantly, also a positive association between smoking and high monthly income of the family found to be critical for students smoking.

REFERENCES

1. Abdel-Hamid E. Drug abuse among Zagazig university students. An epidemiological study. *Egyptian Journal of occupational medicine*, 2000; 24: 219-236.
2. Almutairi K. Tobacco Prevalence among Health Sciences College Students (HSC): Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Middle East journal of family medicine*, 2010; 8(7).
3. Halperin A., Smith S., Heiligenstein E., Brown D., Fleming M. Cigarette smoking and associated health risks among students at five universities. *Nicotine Tob Res.*, 2010; 12(2): 96-104.
4. Flaherty J.A., Richman J.A. Substance use and addiction among medical students, residents, and physicians. *Psychiatr Clin North Am*, 1993; 16(1): 189-197.

5. Baška T., Warren C., Hudečková H., Ochaba R., Šťastný P., Lea V., Lee, J. The role of family background on cigarette smoking among adolescent school children in Slovakia: findings from the 2007 Slovakia Global Youth Tobacco Survey. *International Journal of Public Health*, 2010; 55(6): 591-597.
6. Siddiqui S., Ogbeide D. Profile of smoking amongst health staff in a primary care unit at a general hospital in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Med J.*, 2001; 22: 1101-1104.
7. Behbehani N., Hamadeh R., Macklai N. Knowledge of and attitude towards tobacco control among smoking and nonsmoking physicians in 2 Gulf Arab States. *Saudi Med J.*, 2004; 25: 585-591.
8. Khoja T., Farid S. Saudi Arabia Family Health Survey. Riyadh: Council of Health Ministries of GCC States, 2000; 78-81.
9. Ellickson, P.L., Tucker, J.S., Klein, D.J. High-risk behaviours associated with early smoking: results from a 5-year follow-up. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 2001; 28(6): 465-473.
10. White, H.R., Padina, R.J., Chen, P.H. Developmental trajectories of cigarette use from early adolescence into young adulthood. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*, 2002; 65(2): 167-11. Maziak W., Ward K.D., Afifi Soweid R.A., Eissenberg T. Standardizing questionnaire items for the assessment of water-pipe tobacco use in epidemiological studies. *Public Health*, 2005; 119(5): 400-404.
11. World Health Organization. Guidelines for controlling and monitoring the tobacco epidemic. Geneva: WHO, 1998.
12. Singh S.K., Narang R.K., Chandra S., Chaturvedi P.K., Dubey A.L. Smoking habits of the medical students. *Indian J Chest Dis Allied Sci.*, 1989; 31: 99-103.
13. Prevalence of Tobacco Use in Karnataka and Uttar Pradesh in India (2001): Available at: www.searo.who.int/en/Section1174/Section1462/pdfs/surv/SentinelIndia2001
14. El-Sharkawy Ghada F. Cigarette Smoking among University Students: Family- related & Personal risk factors. *Journal of American Science*, 2011; 7(3): 260-268.
15. Mandil A., Hussein A., Omer H., Turki G., Gaber I. Characteristics and risk factors of tobacco consumption among University of Sharjah students, 2005. *Eastern Mediterranean health journal EMRJ*, 2007; 13(6).
16. Mukhtar A., Gadallah S., Aboul Fatouh A., El-Setouhy M. Magnitude of smoking behavior and some related attributes among rural secondary school students in Qalyobia Governorate. *The Egyptian Journal of community medicine*, 2006; 24(1): 41-59.
17. Hann N. and Asghar A. Smoking in Oklahoma: The seven-year trend. *J Okla state Med Assoc*, Mar. 1997; 90(3): 94-100.

18. Challier B., Chau N., Predine R., Choquet M., Legras B. Associations of family environment and individual factors with tobacco, alcohol and illicit drug use in adolescents. *European J of Epidemiology*, 2000; 16(1): 33-42.
19. Nassar H. The economics of tobacco in Egypt. A new analysis of demand. Health, nutrition and population discussion paper. Washington, DC, International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/World Bank, 2003.
20. Ramakrishna G.S., Sankara Sarma P., Thankappan K.R. Tobacco use among medical students in Orissa. *Natl Med J India*, 2005; 18: 285-289.
21. Nawaz H., Imam S.Z., Zubairi A.B., Pabaney A.H., Sepah Y.J., Islam M., Khan J.A. Smoking habits and beliefs of future physicians of Pakistan, section of pulmonary and critical care medicine, Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan. *Int J Tuberculosis and Lung Diseases*, 2007; 11: 915-919.